

The Role of Trunk Control on Hand Function, Activities of Daily Living, and Quality of Life in Children with Cerebral Palsy

Serebral Palsili Çocuklarda Gövde Kontrolünün El Fonksiyonu, Günlük Yaşam Aktiviteleri ve Yaşam Kalitesi Üzerindeki Rolü

Melike MÜSEVİTOĞLU, Uzm.Fzt. ¹, Feride YARAR, Doç. Dr. ²

¹Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University, Vocational School of Health Services, Karaman, Türkiye

²Pamukkale University, Faculty of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Denizli, Türkiye

Öz

Amaç: Bu çalışma, hemiparetik ve diparetik Serebral Palsi (SP)'li çocuklarda gövde kontrolünün el fonksiyonu, günlük yaşam aktiviteleri ve yaşam kalitesi üzerindeki etkisini değerlendirmeyi amaçlamaktadır.

Yöntem: Kaba Motor Sınıflandırma Sistemi seviye I-III olarak sınıflandırılan, ambulatuar 46 SP'li çocuk çalışmaya dahil edildi. Çocuklar, medyan Gövde Kontrol Ölçüm Skalası (GKÖS) skoru (42,50) temel alınarak yüksek (Grup 1, n = 23) ve düşük (Grup 2, n = 23) gövde kontrolüne sahip olarak iki gruba ayrıldı. El fonksiyonu 9-Delikli Peg Testi (9-DPT) ile, günlük yaşam aktiviteleri Pediatrik Fonksiyonel Bağımsızlık Ölçeği (PFBÖ) ile ve yaşam kalitesi Çocuklar İçin Yaşam Kalitesi Ölçeği (ÇiYKÖ) ile değerlendirildi.

Sonuçlar: Daha yüksek gövde kontrolüne sahip çocuklar, daha düşük gövde kontrolüne sahip olanlara kıyasla dominant el 9-DPT performansında ($p=0,005$) ve PFBÖ skorlarında ($p=0,001$) anlamlı derecede daha iyi sonuçlar göstermiştir. Tüm GKÖS parametreleri ile PFBÖ arasında orta-düşük düzeyde pozitif korelasyonlar bulunmuştur ($r=0,455-0,568$, $p<0,01$). Dominant el 9-DPT performansı

ile GKÖS parametreleri arasında ise orta-düşük düzeyde negatif korelasyonlar saptanmıştır ($r=-0,422-0,601$, $p<0,01$). ÇiYKÖ parametreleri veya non-dominant el 9-DPT performansı ile anlamlı bir ilişki bulunmamıştır ($p>0,05$).

Tartışma: Bozulmuş gövde kontrolü, dominant el fonksiyonu ve günlük yaşam aktiviteleri ile ilişkili bulunmuş, ancak non-dominant el fonksiyonu veya yaşam kalitesi ile ilişkili bulunmamıştır. El fonksiyonu ve günlük yaşam aktiviteleri ile olan ilişkisi göz önünde bulundurulduğunda, gövde kontrolü değerlendirme sürecine dahil edilmelidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Günlük yaşam aktiviteleri, Serebral palsy, El fonksiyonu, Yaşam kalitesi, Gövde kontrolü

Abstract

Purpose: This study aims to evaluate the impact of trunk control on hand function, daily living activities, and quality of life in children with hemiparetic and diparetic Cerebral Palsy (CP).

Methods: We included 46 ambulatory children with CP classified at Gross Motor Function Classification System levels I-III. Children were divided into two groups based on the median Trunk Control Measurement Scale (TCMS) score (42.50): those with higher trunk control (Group 1, n = 23) and those with lower trunk control (Group 2, n = 23). We evaluated their hand function using 9-Hole Peg Test (9-HPT), activities of daily living (ADLs) using Functional Independence Measure for Children (WeeFIM), and quality of life using Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory (PedsQL).

Results: Children with higher trunk control demonstrated significantly better 9-HPT dominant hand function ($p=0.005$) and higher scores in WeeFIM ($p=0.001$) compared to those with lower trunk control. Moderate to low positive correlations were found between all TCMS parameters and WeeFIM ($r=0.455$ to 0.568 , $p<0.01$), while 9-HPT dominant hand function showed moderate to low negative correlations with TCMS parameters ($r=-0.422$ to -0.601 , $p<0.01$). No significant associations were observed with PedsQL parameters or 9-HPT non-dominant hand function ($p>0.05$).

Conclusion: Impaired trunk control was associated with dominant hand function and ADLs, but not with non-dominant hand function or quality of life. Considering its relationship with hand function and ADLs, trunk control should be incorporated into the assessment process.

Keywords: Activities of daily living, Cerebral Palsy, Hand function, Quality of life, Trunk control

1. Introduction

Cerebral Palsy (CP) is described as “a group of permanent disorders of the development of movement and posture, causing activity limitation, that are attributed to nonprogressive disturbances that occurred in the developing fetal or infant brain” (1). Abnormalities in muscle tone and movement lead to impaired postural control, in which the trunk plays a key role by organizing balance reactions and maintaining stability (2,3). Trunk control has an essential role in daily life, such as sitting, standing, reaching, and maintaining a stable upright posture of the trunk and head against gravitational forces (4). Therefore, trunk control contributes to upper extremity function and activities of daily living (ADLs), and may even have an impact on quality of life (5–7).

Hand function is the capacity to manage ADLs that require the use of the upper extremity (8). In children with CP, hand function, defined as the ability to use the hands functionally in various contexts, is often limited (9). This constraint is associated with various upper limb impairments, such as reduced fine motor control, impaired manual dexterity, and decreased grip strength (9). Children with such impairments commonly struggle with core motor functions, including object-directed actions like pointing, reaching, grasping, holding, releasing, and throwing. These motor deficits often translate into significant challenges in self-care domains such as feeding, grooming, hygiene, and dressing, thereby limiting

their independence in ADLs and diminishing their overall functional participation (9,10). ADLs are fundamental to living in a social world, as they ensure basic survival and well-being (11). In this context, it has been argued that the focus regarding individuals with disabilities should not be limited to functional limitations alone, but should also encompass more comprehensive constructs that reflect overall well-being, such as health-related quality of life (12).

The World Health Organization defines quality of life as “an individual's perception of their position in life within the context of the culture and value systems in which they live, and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns” (13). Therefore, in order for the services provided to children with CP to be effective and meaningful, it is of great importance that professionals have a solid understanding of the multidimensional nature of quality of life and the factors that influence it (14).

Current researches primarily focus on hand functions, ADLs, and quality of life in children with CP (15,16). However, comprehensive studies simultaneously examining trunk control in relation to hand function, activities of daily living, and quality of life in children with cerebral palsy remain limited. Existing studies are often restricted to one or two domains, and few provide an integrated evaluation of these interrelated outcomes. This study aims to evaluate the impact of trunk control on hand function, activities of daily living, and quality of life in

children with hemiparetic and diparetic cerebral palsy. While previous research has largely focused on these outcomes in isolation, the present study considers these domains together within a single framework, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of their interrelated effects on functional performance.

2. Materials And Methods

Study Design, Sample Size, and Participants

This cross-sectional study was conducted with children diagnosed with CP who were enrolled in rehabilitation programs at special education and rehabilitation centers in Konya. The participants were receiving rehabilitation once a week, with each session lasting approximately 2 hours. Necessary permissions were obtained from the participating centers, and ethical approval was obtained from the Pamukkale University Medical Ethics Committee (approval number: 60116787-020/92630). Written and verbal informed consent was obtained from the parents of the children who agreed to participate in the study. The procedures used in this study adhere to the tenets of the Declaration of Helsinki. According to the power analysis, when at least 38 individuals were included in the study (at least 19 individuals for each group), it was calculated that 80% power could be obtained at the 95% confidence level (Cohen's $d=0.95$) (17).

As shown in Figure 1, 65 children were initially assessed; 10 did not meet the inclusion criteria, 5 declined to participate, and 4 were excluded due to other reasons (lack of cooperation and withdrawal during the assessment

process). Consequently, a total of 46 children completed the study. Figure 1 illustrates the flow of participants through the processes of eligibility assessment, exclusion, enrollment, and study completion. Children were eligible to participate in the study if they (a) were between 5 and 18 years of age; (b) had a diagnosis of hemiparetic or diparetic CP; and (c) were classified within levels I to III of the Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS). Children who had undergone orthopedic surgery of the upper extremities and/or received Botulinum Toxin-A injections within the past six months were excluded. Additionally, children who were unable to comprehend and follow simple verbal instructions were also excluded from the study. This was determined during the initial assessment based on the child's ability to understand and respond to simple age-appropriate verbal commands, as judged by the evaluating physiotherapist.

Figure 1. Participant Flow Diagram

Assessment

All assessments were conducted by the same physiotherapist to ensure consistency. The evaluations were performed in a single session for each participant and lasted approximately 30-45 minutes in total. The assessment protocol was administered in a standardized order, starting with trunk control evaluation, followed by hand function, activities of daily living, and quality of life assessments. Short rest periods were provided between tests as needed to minimize fatigue and maintain the child's attention and performance. The primary outcome

of this study was trunk control, assessed using the Trunk Control Measurement Scale (TCMS). In addition, the 9-Hole Peg Test (9-HPT), the Functional Independence Measure for Children (WeeFIM), and the Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory (PedsQL) were employed to evaluate hand function, ADLs, and quality of life, respectively. The TCMS does not have an established cut-off score. Therefore, the median TCMS score was used to categorize participants into two groups, allowing for comparison between relatively higher and lower trunk control levels in the absence of a clinically defined threshold (18). Based on the median TCMS score (42.50), children with CP were divided into two groups: Group 1 (higher trunk control, n = 23) and Group 2 (lower trunk control, n = 23).

Trunk Control Measurement Scale (TCMS): TCMS assesses two key components of trunk control during functional activities. It comprises two main sections: static sitting balance and dynamic sitting balance. The static sitting balance subscale evaluates trunk stability during both lower and upper extremity movements. The dynamic sitting balance section includes two subcomponents: selective movement control and dynamic reaching. The scale consists of 15 items, with a total score ranging from 0 to 58 points, where higher scores reflect better trunk control performance (19). The ICC value of the inter-rater reliability for the TCMS is 0.823–0.886, and the intra-rater reliability is 0.986–0.992 (20). Children were evaluated in a quiet and well-lit room. Any orthoses, shoes, and/or trunk supports were removed prior to assessment. For the starting position, each participant was seated at the edge of

a treatment table without back, arm, or foot support, with the thighs fully in contact with the table surface. Children were instructed to sit upright and were encouraged to maintain this posture throughout the assessment (20).

9-Hole Peg Test (9-HPT): 9-HPT is a test that is simple, fast, requires minimal space and equipment (21,22). The test consists of a square board with nine holes. In a quiet room, the children were assessed while seated in a chair positioned in front of a table (21). Hand dominance was determined by asking the children or their caregivers. The children were instructed to insert the pegs into the holes as quickly as possible using their dominant hand and then remove them immediately after insertion. Each participant completed a single trial. The same procedure was then repeated with the non-dominant hand. The time taken to complete the test was recorded in seconds, with lower scores indicating better hand function (23).

Functional Independence Measure for Children (WeeFIM): The scale consists of 18 items grouped under six subdomains: self-care (6 items), sphincter control (2 items), mobility/transfers (3 items), locomotion (2 items), communication (2 items), and social cognition (3 items). Each item is scored on a 7-point scale, where a score of 1 indicates complete dependence and a score of 7 indicates complete independence. The total score ranges from a minimum of 18 to a maximum of 126 (24). The scale demonstrates high reliability, with Cronbach's alpha and ICC values ranging between 0.91 and 0.98 (25). In this study, the WeeFIM was completed based on parent-reported information.

Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory (PedsQL): This scale was developed by Varni et al. (26) to assess the quality of life in children aged 2 to 18 with healthy, acute, or chronic health conditions, and consists of a total of 23 items. The PedsQL includes both child self-report and parent proxy-report forms. Child self-report forms are available for ages 5–7, 8–12, and 13–18 years, while parent proxy-report forms are available for ages 2–4, 5–7, 8–12, and 13–18 years and assess parents' perceptions of their child's quality of life (27). Scoring is conducted across three domains: the total scale score, the physical health, and the psychosocial health, the latter derived from items assessing emotional, social, and school functioning. Each item is scored on a scale from 0 to 100, with higher total PedsQL scores indicating better quality of life (28). The scale demonstrates high internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.70-0.89$) and high clinical reliability (27). The reliability and validity of the Turkish version of the PedsQL were reported by Cakin Memik et al. (29) for children aged 8–12 years, by Memik et al. (28) for adolescents aged 13–18 years, and by Uneri et al. (30) for children aged 2–7 years.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 25.0 (SPSS Inc., IBM Corporation in NY). The Shapiro-Wilk test evaluated all continuous variables in terms of the normality of the data distribution. All analyses were performed using available data, and missing values were excluded from the respective analyses. Continuous variables were presented as means and standard deviations

(SD) for normally distributed data, and as medians and interquartile ranges and percentiles for non-normally distributed data. Categorical variables were analyzed using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test to examine participants' characteristics. We used the Mann-Whitney U test to compare the groups in terms of their TCMS, 9-HPT and WeeFIM scores. Independent Samples t test was used to compare the groups in terms of their PedsQL scores, as the data were normally distributed. Spearman's correlation test analyzed the correlation between the outcome measures. We considered statistical significance to be $p < 0.05$.

3.Results

This study included 46 children with hemiparetic and diparetic CP (8 females, 38 males). Mean ages of children in Group 1 and Group 2 were 11.86 ± 4.21 years and 10.43 ± 4.24 years, respectively. Demographic characteristics of groups are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Groups

		Group 1 (n=23)	Group 2 (n=23)	p
Age (years, Mean \pm SD) [§]		11.86 \pm 4.21	10.43 \pm 4.24	0.256
Weight (kg, Median (IQR)) [†]		34.00 (28.00-42.00)	30.00 (25.00-40.00)	0.468
Height (cm, Mean \pm SD) [§]		141.82 \pm 26.37	129.80 \pm 21.55	0.098
	n (%)	n (%)	p	
Gender [‡]	Female	6 (26.10)	2 (8.70)	0.243
	Male	17 (73.90)	21 (91.30)	
Dominant side [†]	Right	12 (52.20)	14 (60.90)	0.552
	Left	11 (47.80)	9 (39.10)	
CP type [†]	Hemiparetic	13 (56.50)	11 (47.80)	0.555
	Diparetic	10 (43.50)	12 (52.20)	

CP: Cerebral Palsy, [‡]: Median (Interquartile Range) and used Mann-Whitney U test, [§]: Mean \pm Standard Deviation and used Independent Sample t test, [†]: Fisher's Exact test, [‡]: Chi-Square test, * $p < 0.05$

Table 2. Comparison of Trunk Control, Hand Function, Activities of Daily Living and Quality of Life Parameters Between Groups

		Group 1 (n)	Group 2 (n)	z/t	p
TCMS	Static sitting balance ^δ	20.00 (19.00-23)	14.00 (8.00-16.00)	-5.464 ^z	<0.001*
	Selective movement control ^δ	21.00 (18.00-23)	11.00 (4.00-16.00)	-5.407 ^z	<0.001*
	Dynamic reaching ^δ	9.00 (7.00-10.00)	7.00 (5.00-8.00)	-3.221 ^z	0.001*
	Total TCMS score ^δ	49.00 (45.00-52.00)	31.00 (24.00-39.00)	-5.817 ^z	<0.001*
9-HPT	Dominant hand ^δ	27.39 (23.67-33.67)	36.20 (27.53-47.84)	-2.816 ^z	0.005*
	Non-dominant hand ^δ	50.68 (37.67-102.69)	52.09 (31.61-81.91)	-0.423 ^z	0.673
WeeFIM	Total WeeFIM score ^δ	123.00 (111.00-126.00)	100.00 (95.00-111.00)	-3.317 ^z	0.001*
PedsQL	Physical health ^γ	58.13 ± 19.03 (23)	60.28 ± 18.02 (23)	-0.394 ^t	0.695
	Psychosocial health ^γ	69.70 ± 13.85 (23)	65.60 ± 16.94 (23)	0.899 ^t	0.373
	Total PedsQL score ^γ	65.73 ± 11.91 (23)	63.89 ± 13.49 (23)	0.491 ^t	0.626

^z: Mann-Whitney U test, ^t: Independent Sample T test, TCMS: Trunk Control Measurement Scale, 9-HPT: 9-Hole Peg Test, WeeFIM: Functional Independence Measure for Children, PedsQL: Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory, ^δ: expressed as Median (Interquartile Range), ^γ: Mean ± Standart Deviation, *p<0.05

Footnote: Variations in sample size (n) reflect missing data resulting from some participants' inability to complete specific assessments.

Table 2 shows the comparisons of the groups in terms of trunk control, hand function, ADLs, and quality of life. Group 1 exhibited a significantly higher static sitting balance ($z=-5.464$, $p<0.001$), selective movement control ($z=-5.407$, $p<0.001$), dynamic reaching ($z=-3.221$, $p=0.001$), and total TCMS score ($z=-5.817$, $p<0.001$).

Group 1 demonstrated a statistically significant lower score on the 9-HPT for the dominant hand ($z=-2.816$, $p=0.005$). Group 1 showed significantly higher scores in ADLs ($z=-3.317$, $p=0.001$). Quality of life scores did not differ significantly between the groups ($p>0.05$).

Table 3 presents the correlations of parameters related to trunk control. The 9-HPT dominant hand scores showed a moderate negative correlation with selective movement control ($r=-0.601$, $p<0.001$), a low negative correlation with dynamic reaching ($r=-0.422$, $p=0.004$), a moderate negative correlation with the total TCMS score ($r=-0.554$, $p<0.001$), and a low negative correlation with the total WeeFIM score ($r=-0.328$, $p=0.032$). There were positive correlations of low to moderate between ADLs and all trunk control parameters (respectively: static sitting balance, $r=0.476$, $p=0.001$; selective movement control, $r=0.455$, $p=0.002$; dynamic reaching, $r=0.522$, $p<0.001$; total TCMS score, $r=0.568$, $p<0.001$). No significant correlations were found between quality of life or 9-HPT non-dominant hand scores and any of the assessed parameters ($p>0.05$).

Table 3. Correlations Between Trunk Control, Hand Function, Activities of Daily Living and Quality of Life Parameters

		9-HPT		WeeFI		PedsQL	
		Dominant hand	Non-dominant hand	Total WeeFI M score	Physical health	Psychosocial health	Total PedsQL L score
Static sitting balance	r	-0.285	0.042	0.476	-0.068	0.182	0.034
	p	0.058	0.802	0.001*	0.654	0.226	0.824
Selective movement	r	-0.601	0.002	0.455	-0.161	-0.028	-0.168
	p	<0.001*	0.989	0.002*	0.286	0.856	0.265
TCM S	r	-0.422	-0.207	0.522	-0.157	0.090	-0.089
	p	0.004*	0.207	<0.001*	0.299	0.552	0.556
Total	r	-0.554	-0.030	0.568	-0.142	0.075	-0.099
	p	<0.001*	0.855	<0.001*	0.347	0.619	0.513

r: Spearman's correlation test, TCMS: Trunk Control Measurement Scale, 9-HPT: 9-Hole Peg Test, WeeFIM: Functional Independence Measure for Children, PedsQL: Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory, *p < 0.05

4. Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the effects of trunk control on hand function, ADLs, and quality of life in children with hemiparetic and diparetic CP. The findings revealed that better trunk control was associated with improved dominant hand function and enhanced performance in ADLs. However, trunk control did not appear to have a significant impact on overall quality of life.

In the present study, children with higher trunk control demonstrated higher ADL scores compared to those with lower trunk control. This may be attributed to the fact that adequate trunk control provides proximal stability, facilitating coordinated limb movements and efficient postural adjustments required for the performance of ADLs. Given that many ADLs involve coordinated upper and lower extremity movements, and that trunk control provides a stable base for such movements, insufficient

trunk stability may compromise functional independence (7). Furthermore, impairments in trunk control associated with muscle weakness, disrupted neural pathways, and abnormal postural mechanics have been shown to negatively affect functional activities such as sitting, standing, and walking (3,4,31). In children with hemiparetic CP, both static and dynamic postural stability have been shown to be significantly impaired compared to typically developing peers (32) while in diparetic CP, trunk instability—characterized by increased center of pressure oscillations—contributes to balance deficits (33).

In addition, reductions in trunk muscle thickness, particularly in muscles such as the rectus abdominis, have been associated with decreased ADL performance in individuals with CP (34). Consistent with our findings, previous studies have demonstrated a significant association between trunk control and ADLs in children with CP (7,16,35), highlighting the importance of trunk control as a fundamental component of functional independence.

In the present study, a significant relationship was observed between trunk control and dominant hand performance, whereas no such relationship was found for the non-dominant hand as measured by the 9-HPT. The association observed for the dominant hand may be explained by its more frequent use in daily activities, which promotes better motor control and coordination and increases reliance on trunk stability during task performance. Adequate trunk control provides a stable proximal base, facilitating efficient distal movements (36).

In contrast, the lack of association for the non-dominant hand may be attributed to its reduced functional use and lower motor experience in children with CP, which may limit the extent to which trunk control influences its performance. Additionally, increased time spent in seated postures with age may contribute to improved postural control in sitting (37), potentially reducing the reliance on trunk control during fine motor tasks performed with the non-dominant hand. Furthermore, postural challenges during reaching tasks have been linked to decreased movement smoothness in children with CP (38), suggesting that trunk stability may play a more prominent role in functionally demanding upper extremity tasks. These findings are consistent with previous reports indicating that trunk stabilizer muscles play a critical role in force generation and transfer, and that proximal stability enables more efficient movement of distal segments, thereby enhancing functional performance (36). This finding may also be explained by the nature of bimanual task performance, as such tasks often require different roles for each hand and do not necessitate equal manipulative abilities (39). Rather than the degree of asymmetry, proficiency in the dominant hand appears to be a key determinant of bimanual skill (40). Moreover, the ability to manipulate objects in multiple ways during bimanual tasks (39) may allow compensation for limitations in the non-dominant hand, which may explain why ADL performance is more closely associated with dominant hand function than with non-dominant hand function.

In the present study, no significant difference was found between groups with higher and lower trunk control in terms of quality of life. This finding may be explained by the multifactorial nature of quality of life in children with CP, which is influenced not only by physical abilities but also by individual and environmental factors (14,41). Although trunk control contributes to physical function, its direct impact on perceived quality of life may be limited, particularly in children with relatively preserved motor function. In line with our findings, previous research has reported no significant association between gross motor function and quality of life in ambulatory children and adolescents with CP (GMFCS levels I–II) (42). These findings suggest that improvements in physical components such as trunk control may not directly translate into changes in overall quality of life, which encompasses broader physical, emotional, and social dimensions, and may instead be mediated by contextual and psychosocial factors rather than solely by motor-related factors.

Limitations and Future Research

This study has several limitations. First, only children with GMFCS levels I to III were included; therefore, the findings cannot be generalized to all GMFCS levels. Second, participants were divided into groups based on the median TCMS score, which may have led to a loss of information and reduced sensitivity by categorizing a continuous variable. Another limitation is the inability to

use computer-assisted measurement methods. Future studies with larger sample sizes, incorporating technology-based assessments and examining additional factors that may influence quality of life, are needed.

Conclusion

In our study, we summarized the effects of trunk control on hand function, ADLs, and quality of life in children with hemiparetic and diparetic CP. Impaired trunk control was associated with dominant hand function and ADLs, but not with non-dominant hand function or quality of life. Considering its relationship with hand function and ADLs, trunk control should be incorporated not only into the assessment process but also into rehabilitation programs. Interventions aimed at improving trunk stability may enhance upper extremity performance and functional independence in daily activities.

Declaration of conflicting interest: The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Funding statement: This study was supported by the Pamukkale University Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit [project numbers 2020 SABE 016].

Acknowledgments: Authors would like thank to all our children with Cerebral Palsy and their parents participated in this study.

References

1. Rosenbaum P, Paneth N, Leviton A, Goldstein M, Bax M, Damiano D, Dan B, Jacobsson B. A report: the definition and classification of cerebral palsy April 2006. *Dev Med Child Neurol Suppl.* 2007;109:8-14.
2. Heyrman L, Desloovere K, Molenaers G, Verheyden G, Klingels K, Monbaliu E, Feys H. Clinical characteristics of impaired trunk control in children with spastic cerebral palsy. *Res Dev Disabil.* 2013;34(1):327-34.
3. Monica S, Nayak A, Joshua AM, Mithra P, Amaravadi SK, Misri Z, Unnikrishnan B. Relationship between trunk position sense and trunk control in children with spastic cerebral palsy: A cross-sectional study. *Rehabil Res Pract.* 2021;2021:9758640.
4. Saether R, Helbostad JL, Adde L, Jørgensen L, Vik T. Reliability and validity of the Trunk Impairment Scale in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy. *Res Dev Disabil.* 2013;34(7):2075-84.
5. Kusumoto Y, Takaki K, Matsuda T, Nitta O. Relevant factors of self-care in children and adolescents with spastic cerebral palsy. *PLoS One.* 2021;16(7):e0254899.
6. López-Ruiz J, Estrada-Barranco C, Martín-Gómez C, Egea-Gámez RM, Valera-Calero JA, Martín-Casas P, López-de-Uralde-Villanueva I. Trunk Control Measurement Scale (TCMS): Psychometric properties of cross-cultural adaptation and validation of the Spanish version. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2023;20(6):5144.
7. Keller JW, Fahr A, Lieber J, Balzer J, Van Hedel HJA. Impact of upper extremity impairment and trunk control on self-care independence in children with upper motor neuron lesions. *Phys Ther.* 2021;101(8):pzab112.
8. Eliasson AC, Krumlinde-Sundholm L, Rösblad B, Beckung E, Arner M, Ohrvall AM, Rosenbaum P. The Manual Ability Classification System (MACS) for children with cerebral palsy: scale development and evidence of validity and reliability. *Dev Med Child Neurol.* 2006;48(7):549-54.
9. Kachmar OO, Mysula IR, Kushnir AD, Fedchysyn BY, Melekh N V. Effect of Professor Kozyavkin method on hand function in children with cerebral palsy. *Int Neurol J.* 2020;16(1):2-9.
10. Arnould C, Bleyenheuft Y, Thonnard JL. Hand functioning in children with cerebral palsy. *Front Neurol.* 2014;5:48.
11. Pashmdarfard M, Amini M, Hassani Mehraban A. Participation of Iranian cerebral palsy children in life areas: A systematic review article. *Iran J Child Neurol.* 2017;11(1):1.
12. Power R, King C, Muhi M, Heaney E, Galea C, Jones C, Badawi N, Khandaker G. Health-related quality of life of children and adolescents with cerebral palsy in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review. *Dev Med Child Neurol.* 2018;60(5):469-79.
13. World Health Organization. Geneva: World Health Organization. 1997. p. 1. Division of Mental Health and Prevention of Substance Abuse (1997) WHOQOL : measuring quality of life.
14. Almasri NA, Alquaqzeh FA. Determinants of quality of life of children and adolescents with cerebral palsy: A systematic review. *Phys Occup Ther Pediatr.* 2023;43(4):367-88.
15. Kim DH, An DH, Yoo WG. The relationship between trunk control and upper limb function in children with cerebral palsy. *Technol Health Care.* 2018;26(3):421-7.

16. Tarfa HB, Hassan AB, Badaru UM, Abdullahi A. Predictors of gross motor function and activities of daily living in children with cerebral palsy. *Int J Rehabil Res.* 2021;44(4):330–5.
17. Yıldız A, Yıldız R, Elbasan B. Trunk control in children with cerebral palsy and its association with upper extremity functions. *J Dev Phys Disabil.* 2018;30(5):669–76.
18. Duray M, Dengiz A, Kavlak E, Tutar S. the effects of trunk impairment on fatigue and balance in children with cerebral palsy. *Percept Mot Skills.* 2023;130(3):1123–38.
19. Heyrman L, Molenaers G, Desloovere K, Verheyden G, De Cat J, Monbaliu E, Feys H. A clinical tool to measure trunk control in children with cerebral palsy: the Trunk Control Measurement Scale. *Res Dev Disabil.* 2011;32(6):2624–35.
20. Ozal C, Ari G, Gunel MK. Inter-intra observer reliability and validity of the Turkish version of Trunk Control Measurement Scale in children with cerebral palsy. *Acta Orthop Traumatol Turc.* 2019;53(5):381–4.
21. Poole JL, Burtner PA, Torres TA, McMullen CK, Markham A, Marcum ML, Anderson JB, Qualls C. Measuring dexterity in children using the Nine-hole Peg Test. *J Hand Ther.* 2005;18(3):348–51.
22. Immerman I, Alfonso DT, Ramos LE, Grossman LA, Alfonso I, Ditaranto P, Grossman JA. Hand function in children with an upper brachial plexus birth injury: results of the nine-hole peg test. *Dev Med Child Neurol.* 2012;54(2):166–9.
23. Mathiowetz V, Weber K, Kashman N, Volland G. Adult norms for the nine hole peg test of finger dexterity. *Occupational Therapy Journal of Research.* 1985;5(1):24–38.
24. Msall ME, DiGaudio K, Rogers BT, LaForest S, Catanzaro NL, Campbell J, Wilczenski F, Duffy LC. The Functional Independence Measure for Children (WeeFIM). Conceptual basis and pilot use in children with developmental disabilities. *Clin Pediatr (Phila).* 1994;33(7):421–30.
25. Tur BS, Küçükdeveci AA, Kutlay Ş, Yavuzer G, Elhan AH, Tennant A. Psychometric properties of the WeeFIM in children with cerebral palsy in Turkey. *Dev Med Child Neurol.* 2009;51(9):732–8.
26. Varni JW, Seid M, Rode CA. The PedsQL: measurement model for the pediatric quality of life inventory. *Med Care.* 1999;37(2):126–39.
27. Varni JW, Seid M, Kurtin PS. PedsQLTM 4.0: Reliability and validity of the Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory™ Version 4.0 Generic Core Scales in healthy and patient populations. *Med Care.* 2001;39(8):800–12.
28. Çakın Memik N, Ağaoglu B, Coşkun A, Üneri ÖŞ, Karakaya I. Çocuklar için yaşam kalitesi ölçeğinin 13-18 yaş ergen formunun geçerlik ve güvenilirliği. *Turk Psikiyatri Derg.* 2007;18(4):353–63.
29. Çakın Memik N, Ağaoglu B, Coşkun A, Karakaya I. Çocuklar için Yaşam Kalitesi Ölçeğinin 8-12 yaş çocuk formunun geçerlilik ve güvenilirliği. *TJCAMH.* 2008;15(2):87–98.
30. Uneri OS, Ağaoglu B, Coşkun A, Memik NC. Validity and reliability of Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory for 2- to 4-year-old and 5- to 7-year-old Turkish children. *Qual Life Res.* 2008;17(2):307–15.
31. Munaf A, Mehboob S, Razzaq M, Younas M, Umair S, Waseem I, Shabir H, Gul S. Effect of trunk exercises on trunk control, balance, and mobility function in children with hemiparetic CP. *PJM&HS.* 2022;16(11):95–8.
32. Kenis-Coskun O, Giray E, Eren B, Ozkok O, Karadag-Saygi E. Evaluation of postural stability in children with hemiplegic cerebral palsy. *J Phys Ther Sci.* 2016;28(5):1398.
33. Sah A, Balaji G, Agrahara S. Effects of task-oriented activities based on neurodevelopmental therapy principles on trunk control, balance, and gross motor function in children with spastic diplegic cerebral palsy: A single-blinded randomized clinical trial. *J Pediatr Neurosci.* 2019;14(3):120–6.
34. Masaki M, Isobe H, Uchikawa Y, Okamoto M, Chiyoda Y, Katsuhara Y, Mino K, Aoyama K, Nishi T, Ando Y. Association of gross motor function and activities of daily living with muscle mass of the trunk and lower extremity muscles, range of motion, and spasticity in children and adults with cerebral palsy. *Dev Neurorehabil.* 2023;26(2):115–22.
35. Kallem Seyyar G, Aras B, Aras O. Trunk control and functionality in children with spastic cerebral palsy. *Dev Neurorehabil.* 2019;22(2):120–5.
36. Kibler W Ben, Press J, Sciascia A. The role of core stability in athletic function. *Sports Med.* 2006;36(3):189–98.
37. Seyhan K, Günel MK. Bilateral spastik serebral palsili çocuklarda farklı oturma pozisyonlarının üst ekstremitte fonksiyonuna etkisi. *J Exerc Ther Rehabil.* 2016;2(1):15–20.
38. Ju YH, Hwang IS, Cherng RJ. Postural adjustment of children with spastic diplegic cerebral palsy during seated hand reaching in different directions. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil.* 2012;93(3):471–9.
39. Sakzewski L, Ziviani J, Boyd R. The relationship between unimanual capacity and bimanual performance in children with congenital hemiplegia. *Dev Med Child Neurol.* 2010;52(9):811–6.
40. Klevberg GL, Østensjø S, Krumlinde-Sundholm L, Elkjær S, Jahnsen RB. Hand function in a population-based sample of young children with unilateral or bilateral cerebral palsy. *Phys Occup Ther Pediatr.* 2017;37(5):528–40.
41. Pinquart M. Health-related quality of life of young people with and without chronic conditions. *J Pediatr Psychol.* 2020;45(7):780–92.
42. Chen CM, Chen CY, Wu KP, Chen CL, Hsu HC, Lo SK. Motor factors associated with health-related quality-of-life in ambulatory children with cerebral palsy. *Am J Phys Med Rehabil.* 2011;90(11):940–7.